

THE CHARACTERISTICS OF EDUCATIONAL MIGRATION AMONG UZBEK STUDENTS

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Abstract: Today, studying at popular universities in developed countries is one of the goals of Uzbek youths. Achieving this goal requires several skills from young people, particularly language proficiency, fundamental knowledge in their field, and financial affordability. These factors prevent many young people from achieving this goal, and only those who can find solutions to such problems will have the opportunity to study abroad in developed countries of higher education.

1. Introduction

This article is about the Uzbek youth who have overcome such obstacles and are improving their knowledge in the most developed countries of the world, the paths they have taken to achieve this goal and the main factors in achieving these achievements, difficulties encountered in adapting to higher education, the process of acculturation, peculiarities of foreign elite education system are revealed based on the point of view of Uzbek youth. The above issues are considered based on the acculturation model of human development, neoliberalism, identity issues, and majorism, which are considered anthropological concepts. Thus, the background of Uzbek students, the goals of studying abroad, and the academic difficulties experienced there are revealed, and it provides important information for the education system working with international students, especially Uzbek students.

2. The possible impact of students' background toward their aim

The main theoretical question in this article is why studying abroad matters for Uzbek students. Firstly, we examine the backgrounds and paths of international Uzbek students who have achieved their study abroad goals. Eulalie van Heerden's article "Black University Students in South Africa: The Influence of Sociocultural Factors on Study and Performance" examines the impact of backgrounds, particularly, social and cultural factors on students' academic success [1]. According to him, a child's school education, learning styles, study habits and attitudes, language, country's policy on education, economic and physical environmental factors, individual character, norms and values are essential for his future academic success and successful career [1]. Based on this article, the paths taken by Uzbek students in achieving academic success, and the extent to some social and cultural factors have an influence should be studied in order to fully understand the character of educational migration of Uzbek students. Theoretical question: To what extent are influential social and cultural factors to Uzbek students for their academic achievement? Urie Bronfenbrenner's bio-ecological theory of human development is used as a theory. According to the theory, the micro-system, which is the family and school; the meso-system, which is the collaboration of these two micro-systems; the exo-system, which is the factors that surround the child: the profession of the parents, and the neighborhood; and the macro-system, which is cultural, political, and environmental factors, are important in human development [1]. Additionally, the acculturation processes experienced by students after coming to the host country and their attitude toward the host culture should be studied. Yuri Zhan studied the acculturation processes of Korean students who came to the USA, their ability to adapt to a new culture, and their attitudes towards heritage culture and host culture, based on Berry's bi-dimensional model of acculturation framework in his article entitled "A Bidimensional Model of Acculturation for Korean American Older Adults". According to the article, there are four types of acculturation: integration, assimilation, separation, and marginalization [2]. Based on personal characteristics, students undergo an adaptation process that falls into one of the four types mentioned above. In this article, the adaptation processes of Uzbek students are also seemed to be researched based on the bi-dimensional model of acculturation [2]. Theoretical question: How do Uzbek students experience adaptation to the new culture?

3. The difference of educational system of West and East

Secondly, the effectiveness of the educational system in foreign universities, in particular, the lecture-tutorial model, learning and teaching approach, assessment method in the study of Uzbek students, the uniqueness and significance of the Eastern and Western education systems should be researched. Wang's article "Academic acculturation in 2 + 2 joint programs: students' perspectives" reveals the attitude of Chinese students to the education system in Australian universities and how effective the system is for Asian students

[3]. According to him, some cultures in Eastern education do not correspond to the Western education system, and as a result, students may not be able to achieve their full potential. For example, in the Asian education system, the teacher is dominant in the classes, while in the West, there are student-centered classes. Western students can give counterarguments against the teacher's opinion, and Eastern students see this as disrespect to the teacher. Demerat's 2020 Council on Anthropology & Education Presidential Address Decolonizing Education: Roles for Anthropology article states that one of the main goals of decolonization of education is that teaching methods should be effective for all students and should be free of colonial heritage [4]. Theoretical question: How is the western education system efficiency for uzbek students?

4. Majorism: the process of choosing majors by international students

Thirdly, it is highly relevant to discuss how the students' knowledge from their time overseas efficiently improves their practicality upon returning home. As noted in Carrigan's article "Majorism: Neoliberalism in Student Culture", a lot of today's youth select their higher education majors according to the market economy, social demands, pay, and status of the time [5]. Many civilizations are moving toward privatizing their universities. Universities raise tuition as a result to compensate for their expenses and give priority to revenue. As a result, the standard of education in HE (higher education) declines [5]. The UK HE system started to transform its educational system into employability and competency, based on economic considerations, starting in the 1980s, according to Houtman's article Why Education Matters to Anthropology: An Interview with Sue Wright [6]. In doing so, the reasons behind the Uzbek students' major selection as well as the applicability of the knowledge and experiences they acquired overseas upon returning home will be studied. This topic is studied based on the neoliberalism conception. Theoretical question: How does neoliberalism shape uzbek students' aim in selecting their major in international abroad? To what extent is abroad education knowledge practical in terms of career and work?

5. Identical issues

In the last part, the identity issue of Uzbek students should be studied. In Lee's article "The Themes and Objects of American Educational Anthropology and its Enlightenment for Chinese Educational Anthropology Studies: Based on the Analysis of Anthropology and Education Quarterly", he said that one of the urgent issues that should be studied in today's educational anthropology is the identity issue [7]. In addition, Gita's article "Negotiating and Reinventing Identities by South Asian Women in the Context of Transnational Mobility" is about wives leaving jobs and positions with good prestige in their home countries for their husbands who come to the USA to study. However, in the USA, the work experience and knowledge they have gained in their own country are undervalued, as a result of which they have many difficulties in finding a job and fall under stress [8]. What do the Uzbek students who came abroad for master's and doctoral studies experience regarding the identity issues. How important is the knowledge and experience they have gained in Uzbekistan abroad?

6. Conclusion

To conclude, it can be seen that dozens of anthropologists and educators have been interesting in studying educational migration topics and relevant issues around it due to global increase of this trend. As one of the citizens of Uzbekistan, I can also state that this trend is also really well-spread among uzbek youths in recent years. Hence, as an educator and lecturer, I try to map the main issues and offer some ways of studying the character of educational migration of uzbek students all around the world. In the next step, these suggestions can be employed by researchers in order to understand the real issues of this trend in Uzbekistan and Central Asia.

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